

Appendix C – Interview Protocol

Demographic Information

- Can you briefly tell me about yourself?
- Considering your experience, how many years of experience do you have in the software industry?
- How many years of experience do you have in requirement engineering these years?
- Can you think of your current software engineering project where you were engaged in RE activities?
 - Can you please tell me very briefly about that project?
 - What RE-related activities were being performed on that project?
 - What was your involvement in those activities?

Views on the influence of personality in RE-related activities

Explanation: Personality can be simply described as a set of individual differences, including personal habits, skills, memories, behaviours and social relationships that can be affected by the social and cultural development of individuals. There are various personality models that can be used to measure individual personality, and the one you all have used is the Five Factor Model-one of the most used models in this domain. There are five broad dimensions used in common language to describe human personality as follows:

Openness to Experience: Someone who is high on openness to experience tends to appear as imaginative, broad-minded and curious, whereas those at the opposite end of this spectrum prefer routine and favouring conservative values

Conscientiousness: People who are high in conscientiousness tend to be hardworking, organised, able to complete tasks thoroughly and on time, and reliable. On the other hand, low conscientiousness relates to traits such as being irresponsible, impulsive and disordered.

Extraversion: A person is considered an extravert if he/she feels comfortable in a social relationship, friendly, assertive, active and outgoing

Agreeableness: Refers to traits such as cooperativeness, kindness, trust and warm, whereas people who are low on agreeableness tend to be sceptical, selfish and hostile

Neuroticism: Refers to the state of emotional stability. Someone who is low on Neuroticism tends to appear calm, confident and secure, whereas a high neuroticism individual tends to be moody, anxious, nervous and insecure.

Talking about an individual's personality:

- Have you experienced a person's personality having an effect or impact on how they approach requirements engineering?
 - If yes, can you share your experience?
 - If not, why do you think it does not have any impact?
- Can you think of a time when your own personality (or your team members') positively influenced how they carried out RE activities?
 - Who else did it impact, and how?
- Can you think of a time when your own personality (or someone's) negatively influenced how they carried out RE activities?
 - Who else did it impact, and how?
- Have you experienced your team members' personalities influencing how they carried out RE activities?
 - If yes, can you share your experience?
 - If not, why do you think it does not influence?
- Have you experienced combinations of different personality types impacting RE activities?
 - If yes, can you share your experience?
- How do you handle various personality differences within your team?
- In your experience, are there any other human aspects/ human-centric issues that have an impact on performing RE activities?
 - If yes, what are they?
 - How do they impact?
- Any final thoughts about the impact of personality on RE-related activities?